

Principle of equivalence and general theory of relativity

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Abstract

It was shown that that the general form of the continuous gravitational field metric coincides with the non-inertial system metric describing motion in the Minkowsky space. The result is not a solution of Einstein's equation, which fact requires a revision of a structure of the general relativity theory.

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1. Introduction

The principle of equivalence allows us to do calculations using gravity, looking instead for support frames passing through acceleration. Applying the principle of equivalence, the answer applies equally to the frame of reference with the same acceleration of gravity.

There is no experiment that can be done in a small confined space that can detect the difference between a uniform gravitational field and an equivalent uniform acceleration.

Figure 1. Standard clock in accelerated reference frames and in the gravitational field.

2. Development

More often than not, the general relativity theory is meant to be identifiable with the Einstein’s equation. Indeed, the gravitational field equation allows finding the metrical tensor g_{ik} , defining an acceleration field having an effect on matter and fields.

Nevertheless, the Einstein’s gravity theory is based on the concept about a relation between bodies motion and the geometry of the pseudo-Riemannian space. Let us look at the appearance of the motion equation in the not quite standard form – in the ordinary tridimensional form [1]:

$$\frac{d^2x^i}{dt^2} = -c^2\Gamma_{00}^i - 2c\Gamma_{0k}^i \frac{dx^k}{dt} - \Gamma_{mn}^i \frac{dx^m}{dt} \frac{dx^n}{dt} + \left\{ c\Gamma_{00}^0 + 2\Gamma_{0k}^0 \frac{dx^k}{dt} + \frac{1}{c}\Gamma_{mn}^0 \frac{dx^m}{dt} \frac{dx^n}{dt} \frac{dx^i}{dt} \right\}$$

In particular, in a “motionless” coordinate system, an appearance of a connected-with-a-point gravitational vector is especially simple:

$$\frac{d^2x^i}{dt^2} = -c^2\Gamma_{00}^i \tag{1}$$

Pay attention that the motion equation gives non-zero acceleration not only in Riemannian space but also in reference systems describing motion in an inertial reference system. Any acceleration imposes non-zero Christoffel symbol (1), whether it’d be acceleration caused by a gravitational field, or by body’s curvilinear motion, or by action of other fields.

Thus, the geometrical description of an acceleration field is not connected with a reason caused this acceleration. The metric connected with reference bodies allows calculating accelerations (1); and on contrary, imposing of accelerations of reference bodies applies essential restrictions on the metric connected with those reference bodies.

The simplest field is homogeneous stationary one. In some specified sense, such field is fundamental as in the limit of small 4-volume, any continuous field is homogeneous and stationary. This statement follows from the continuity definition.

It should seem, for a verification of the strong principle of equivalency in the frame of the theory, it is enough to compare a gravitational field, a homogeneous field and a homogeneous field of inertia. Namely this was what V.A. Fock [2] tried doing. However as a homogeneous gravitational field with the potential $\varphi = -\alpha x$ (α is acceleration), Fock chose taking the approximate solution of the Einstein’s equation looked like the expression [2] with the metric

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2\varphi}{c^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 - \left(1 + \frac{2\varphi}{c^2}\right) (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2). \tag{2}$$

As an inertia field, the reference system by Möeller was used:

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2\alpha x}{c^2}\right)^2 c^2 dt^2 - (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2). \quad (3)$$

However neither this nor that metric is homogeneous. More than that, the metric (2) has non-zero tensor of Riemann, while the metric (3) describes a flat space.

Figure 2. An attempt to depict a change temporal and spatial scales homogeneous field along a geodesic.

Таким Thus, Fock’s speculations have turned to be unpersuasive. Nevertheless, this point of view got widespread. Usually, there is given seemingly irresistible argument: bodies’ motion in the pseudo-Euclidean space is described by the special relativity theory; hence the reference system connected with those bodies is flat. However, this statement corresponds to our intuitive concepts about motion and nothing more.

Already the first results belonging to the relativistic gravity theory (Einstein 1907 [4]) showed that own

time in accelerated systems runs differently even in zero-equal speed. Specifically, a tempo of clock run in the accelerated systems depends on a potential of an acceleration field. Much later, this effect was discovered in a gravitational field. These widely known facts not only confirmed the correctness of the general gravity theory once again but also the equivalency principle in its strongest wording (see Fig. 1).

Besides, Einstein made an example of a reference system possessing a constant negative incurvature; such was the reference system connected with a rotating hard disc. The rigorous proof of this affirmation belongs to Moeller [6].

The equation (1) allows obtaining the field metric without connecting it with the Einstein’s equation. Let us impose the homogeneous stationary acceleration field $(\alpha_1, 0, 0)$. From the equation (1), we obtain

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{c^2}{2g_{11}(x)} \frac{dg_{00}(x)}{dx}$$

To this differential equation, it is necessary to add the condition of translation invariance, which means independence of this equation on parallel transfer of coordinates, in particular, at the transformation $x' = x - x_0$. To this condition, the following solution fulfills

$$g_{00}(x) = g_{11}(x) e^{\frac{2\alpha x}{c^2}}.$$

The value $g_{00}(x)$ coincides – in fact – with the result obtained by Einstein [4]. The left elements of the metrical tensor can be found based on isotropy of space:

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2\alpha x}{c^2}} (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2). \quad (4)$$

A metric of any continuous field is a subsequence of infinitesimal metrics (4), see Fig. 2. That is why regardless of a nature of a continuous field metric, the latter is equal to

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2\alpha_{\gamma x_{\gamma}}}{c^2}} (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2). \quad (5)$$

Hence the equivalency principle is proven.

First of all, let us notice that the metrics (4) and (5) have non-zero tensor of Riemann; and its convolutions are non-zero, too. The question now arises, what is seen then by an observer in the Minkowsky space? The answer is simple: the observer sees a projection of geodesic lines of the Riemannian space onto the Minkowsky space. This looks similar to the way how a mountainous terrain is displayed on a flat map.

Notwithstanding, the metric (5) is not a solution of the Einstein's equation. That is why the necessity arises in re-structuring of the general relativity theory, while conserving its principles including the equivalency principle. Some results of such work can be laid out already now [7, 8].

3. Conclusions

Here the equivalence principle is proved. However, this metric is not a solution of the Einstein equation. Therefore There is a need to restructure the general theory of relativity, preserving it Principles, including the principle of equivalence. Certain results of this work can be presented now [7, 8].

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